

TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE THROUGH THE CONTEXT: A TECHNIQUE FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' VOCABULARY

ALI AHMED ALI MANSOOR
Ph.D Scholar,
Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar
Marathwada University,
Aurangabad.

DR. ALKA S. NATHREKAR,
Ph.D. Guide,
Smt. Dankunwar Mahila
Mahaidyalaya, Jalna
Aurangabad.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to find out the effect of the context on improving vocabulary knowledge comprehension of the language. The paper is an out product of fieldwork that is done to laying out some conclusion regarding to the teaching and learning of vocabulary with the help of questionnaire including type of vocabulary questions that gives paper dimension and dissection. The study involved 10 participants who were students in arts of English language as a foreign language (EFL) Jalna college under Dr.BAMU Aurangabad Maharashtra and selected using the random sampling. Data of the study were collected from students after teaching the short story. They were given comprehension questionnaire to know the scope of understanding of the context. The data were analysis by SPSS .The results from the questionnaire indicate that the participants are very much impressed with short story and they are getting the ambiguous words from understanding the context.

INTRODUCTION

The focus of teaching English is shifted nowadays from 'grammaticalized lexis' to 'lexicalized grammar'. the teaching of vocabulary is crucial to communication in general and communication in foreign language in particular. a word has various facets such as phonic, graphic, grammatical, semantic, and pragmatic and context based. The connotation of a word may be different from its denotation. The context chooses the meaning of the word. The situational context and the linguistic context help us to arrive at an appropriate interpretation of a word. The lack of vocabulary cause to lack students understanding of the context. However, reading of the context contributes to improve vocabulary and getting the ambiguous meaning of unknown words. (Students need to see it in context and learn how its meaning relates to words around it. an approach that included definition as well as context can generate a full and flexible knowledge of words meanings). (engageny.2019) teaching context in class help students to improve their vocabulary. Anderson and Freebody (1981) state that (it is the general vocabulary knowledge of the reader that best predicts how well that reader understands the text).

The paper discusses precisely all these aspects in relation to vocabulary. The paper thus talks about learning English language through context. It discusses the effect of learning all of the antonym, synonym, denotation and connotation from short story. It focuses on the context methods, which the teacher uses in the classroom to clarify the text meaning with context. (when academic demands require a deep level of understanding of terms, they will understand to use the words in context, make connections between new and prior knowledge, and apply word meanings across contexts (baker et al., 1995) short story and how it conveys the meaning of words directly through the context is the scope of the paper. furthermore, it discusses what are the benefits of teaching short stories on improving students' vocabulary. all this will be obtained by using questionnaires, which are distributed among the students.

With helping of my supervisor, distributed questionnaire to third year of undergraduate students Arts of English department in Jalna college under Dr. BAMU Aurangabad Maharashtra. The main point of questionnaire to know the effect of context on improving student's comprehension of vocabulary. The Questionnaire were distribute to the students after they had taught the short story. It was under title three-question story By Leo Tolstoy

2. Method

Hypothesis

It is hypothesis that Context improves students' vocabulary comprehension. Learning through context considers the best tool to understand vocabulary meaning.

Question

Does the context improving students' vocabulary comprehension?

Does the learning though context considers the best method to get the real meaning of the word?

Analysis of Questionnaire

In the reality, short stories giving students the main theme of this story to discover the wisdom, goodwill and tolerationthe *three question by short story By Leo Tolstoy*, theme of wisdom, acceptance, kindness, and forgiveness. The story is about the ruler who looking for the correct answer of the three questions to enlightenment his kingdom. He disguised himself then he went to find solutions He met a lot of wises men but without benefit, in the last, he met hermit and he answer his questions. In the following, I tried to get the effect of this short story for student's vocabulary comprehension.

1-. I was your sworn enemy; you killed my brother so I seized ambush. What is the Synonym of ambush? (Trap- frankness-peaceful)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid <i>WRONG</i>	2	20.0	20.0	20.0
<i>CORRECT</i>	8	80.0	80.0	100.0
<i>Total</i>	10	100.0	100.0	

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Out of 10 students participated in the study, 2 (20%) had poor performance in the assessment of comprehension score. And 8 (80%) had average / good performance in the assessment of comprehension score. this result explain that almost of students got benefit of teaching students short stories in classroom. From this side the researcher investigate how short story improve the synonym of vocabulary for undergraduate students.

2- What is the main Messengers that were sent throughout the story of three questions? (i) To fetch wise men (ii) To find answers to the questions. (iii) To look for the wise hermit. (iv) To announce a reward for those who could answer the questions. Mark

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7-Others declared that it was impossible to decide beforehand the right time for every action; What is the antonym of beforehand? (Afterwards-early-previously)

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid CORRECT	10	100.0	100.0	100.0

10 students participated in the study, All students answered correctly, it means that the short story had given students full understanding of the words. They understand the antonym of the words with the really meaning of the words in the context. They possible to use it in another context with same understanding.

Alternatively, they may be replace anther words, which give same meaning.

9-When he had dug two beds; the King stopped and repeated his questions. What is the meaning of the beds? The king broken two sleeping beds The king slept two times in the hermit home It means two hole in the earth

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10 students participated in the study, All students answered correctly, it means that the short story had given students full understanding of the words. They understand the real meaning of the words in the context. They possible to use it in another context with same understanding. The bed means bed, which use for sleeping while in this case use to refer to hole. Which the emperor helped the hermit .so we can say her students has knowledge of homonym of the words.

10-Afterwards when that man ran to us, the most important time was when you were attending to him, for if you had not bound up his wounds he would have died without having made peace with you

What is the denotation of wounds?

The king bound the enemy's stomach

The king solve the enemy's revenge

The king solve the hermit problem

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Conclusion

In this study explained, that short story always helps to answered student's vocabulary comprehension. It improves student's vocabulary knowledge. They understudied what is the real meaning of vocabulary. How to use the words in correct place of sentence. The researcher had given questionnaire to investigate the scope of improving student's vocabulary during teaching short story. Therefore, he got the students who have got out of 80% of students understanding for synonym and denotation of words. And the main idea of context.in other 20% had got out of students poor of understanding synonym and denotation and main idea of the context. From the side of antonym and homonym, shorty story participate for students understating and had given full correct 100% of answer.

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